

New Hydropower Generation System

Invention Title: New Hydropower Generation System with Dual Tanks and Intelligent Pressure Regulation

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Description

This invention introduces a new system for generating electrical energy from water sources. The system consists of two tanks with different elevations (a tall tank and a short tank) that are connected by a lower channel. A separating blade in the middle of the tanks directs the water flow. Water from the tall tank is directed through a pipe to a turbine (such as Pelton or Francis) and causes it to rotate. The mechanical energy of the turbine is converted into electrical energy by a generator. The water exiting the turbine is collected in a funnel-shaped basin and directed to the short tank. An intelligent pressure regulation tube (air chamber) is installed on top of the short tank to stabilize the system and prevent water hammer. The tanks do not have a direct connection to municipal water and can be filled via tankers or independent water sources. Water level adjustment floats automatically control the liquid level in the tanks. This system is suitable for small power plants, remote areas, and industrial applications with increased efficiency, high flexibility, and reliability.

Detailed Technical Description

1. Introduction and Objective

The objective of this invention is to provide an efficient, reliable and flexible hydropower generation system that can exploit the energy potential of water under various conditions. By combining a dual reservoir design, optimized flow guidance, efficient turbine and intelligent pressure regulation mechanism, this system offers significant advantages over existing methods.

2. System Components

a) Dual Reservoir System:

High-Level Reservoir: Serves to store water with high energy potential (high head).

Low-Level Reservoir: Collects water discharged from the turbine.

Lower Connection: A channel or pipe that connects the two reservoirs at the bottom.

Central Dividing Blade: A partition in the middle of the reservoirs that directs the flow of water and prevents complete mixing.

Water supply: The tanks are not connected to city water and can be filled via tanker or independent water sources (river, spring, rainwater).

Water Level Float Regulator: Installed in both tanks to automatically control the water level and prevent overflow or water shortage.

b) Turbine and water guidance system:

Penstock: Water is directed from the high tank to the turbine through this pipe.

Turbine: (Suggested type: Pelton turbine for high head or Francis turbine for medium/high head). The kinetic energy of the water causes the turbine to rotate.

Funnel-Shaped Collector Basin: Located below the turbine, it collects the outlet water and directs it to the short tank.

c) Pressure Regulation System:

Pressure Regulating Tube / Air Vessel: An air chamber above the short tank that regulates the pressure and absorbs fluctuations, prevents water hammer and increases the stability of the system.

3. Energy Generation Process

Water is stored in the long tank and has potential energy.

Water is directed towards the turbine through the penstock tube and potential energy is converted into kinetic energy.

The high-speed flow of water rotates the turbine blades (converting kinetic energy to mechanical energy).

The turbine shaft is connected to a generator and its rotation produces an electric current in the generator (converting mechanical energy to electrical energy).

The water exiting the turbine is collected by a funnel-shaped pan and directed to a short tank.

The pressure regulating tube maintains pressure stability in the system.

4. Innovations and advantages

Dual tank design with separator blade for better flow control.

Ability to supply water via tanker, independent of municipal water.

Use of level adjustment floats for automation.

Efficiency optimization with funnel-shaped basin and pressure adjustment mechanism.

Reduces water hammer effects and increases equipment life.

High flexibility in choosing turbine type and application.

5. Applications

Small-scale power plants, rural and remote areas, energy backup systems, industrial facilities, research projects.

Keywords: Hydropower generation, hydro turbine, dual tank, pressure adjustment, renewable energy, independent system, level adjustment float, water hammer.